

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-XII. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Aryl-3-*p*-(2',4'-diethylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-ylaminobenzoylamino-5*H*/methyl-4-thiazolidinones

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Some new 4-thiazolidinones have been prepared bearing *s*-triazine moiety by the condensation of Schiff bases from *p*-2,4-diethylamino-*s*-triazin-6-ylaminobenzoyl-hydrazine with thioglycolic and thiolactic acid. The structure of the product has been characterised by ir spectral studies. The products have been screened for antimicrobial activity; most of the compounds showed moderate activity.

4-Thiazolidinones have been found to be associated with diverse biological activities and numerous reports have appeared in the literature which highlight their chemistry and use¹. *s*-Triazine derivatives also possess various biological activities².

In continuation of our work on 4-thiazolidinone derivatives³, we have synthesised various 4-thiazolidinones of type 4. Cyanuric chloride (0.1 mol, 18.4 g) was condensed with ethylamine (0.2 mol, 11.2 g) at 37° to get 2,4-diethylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine⁴. The third chlorine atom of cyanuric chloride was replaced by ethyl-*p*-aminobenzoate at 80° to obtain 1 which was further treated with hydrazine hydrate to obtain *p*-2,4-diethylamino-*s*-triazine-6-ylaminobenzoylhydrazine (2). The hydrazide was then condensed with different aromatic aldehydes to get the Schiff bases (3) which on treatment with thioglycolic acid and thiolactic acid gave substituted-4-thiazolidinones (4) (Scheme 1). The structure of the product has been supported by elemental analysis and ir spectral data. The products have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup-plate⁵ method. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 50 µg using gram-positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus* and *S. citreus*, gram-negative bacteria like *Escherichia coli* and *Marcasane serratia*, and fungi like *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Most of the compounds were found moderately active (15–26 mm zone of inhibition) against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

However, comparatively significant activity was observed in compounds bearing aromatic substituents (along with zone of inhibition in mm) $x = H$ and $R = o$ -chlorophenyl (15–22), *p*-chlorophenyl (15–24), cinnamyl (14–23), *o*-methoxyphenyl (13–24) and *m*-nitrophenyl (14–19 mm); $x = CH_3$ and $R = phenyl$

(14-22), 2,4-dichlorophenyl (15-20), *p*-hydroxyphenyl (14-19) and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl (15-23 mm).

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) was taken on a Shimadzu DR-1 435-IR spectrophotometer.

p-2,4-Diethylamino-*s*-triazin-6-ylaminobenzoate : A mixture of 2,4-diethylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol, 2.02 g) and ethyl-*p*-aminobenzoate (0.01 mol, 1.7 g) in dioxane (15 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from dioxane, (73%), m.p. 148° (Found : C, 58.03 ; H, 6.45 ; N, 25.16. C₁₆H₂₂N₆O₂ calcd. for : C, 58.18 ; H, 6.66 ; N, 25.45%).

p-2,4-Diethylamino-*s*-triazin-6-ylaminobenzoylhydrazine : A mixture of *p*-2,4-diethylamino-*s*-triazin-6-ylaminobenzoate (0.01 mol, 3.3 g) in dioxane (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol, 0.52 g) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from dioxane, (78%), m.p. 120° (Found : C, 53.00 ; H, 6.28 ; N, 35.08. C₁₄H₂₀N₈O calcd. for : C, 53.16 ; H, 6.32 ; N, 35.44%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 690 (C=O), 720 (NH wag) and 820 cm⁻¹ (C₈N₈ ring skeletal).

p-2,4-Diethylamino-*s*-triazin-6-ylaminobenzoylbenzaldehyde : A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol, 3.16 g) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol, 1.06 g) in dioxane (15 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (74%), m.p. 150° (Found : C, 62.15 ; H, 5.84 ; N, 27.60. C₂₁H₂₄N₈O calcd. for : C, 62.37 ; H, 5.94 ; N, 27.72%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 600 (C=N) and 820 cm⁻¹ (C₈N₈ ring skeletal).

Similarly, other substituted Schiff bases were prepared (Table 1 ; sl. nos. 1-18).

2-Aryl-3-*p*-(2',4'-diethylamino-*s*-triazin)-6'-ylaminobenzoylamino-5-H-4-thiazolidinones : Thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol, 0.92 g) was added to 3 (0.01 mol, 4.04 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The product was isolated by washing the upper organic layer with water and sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from dioxane, (72%), m.p. 86° (Found : C, 57.68 ; H, 5.38 ; N, 23.02. C₂₃H₂₆N₈O₂S calcd. for : C, 57.74 ; H, 5.44 ; N, 23.43 %) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 325 (NH for thiazolidinone moiety), 1 690 (C=O), 1 585 (C=N), 690 (C-S-C) and 820 cm⁻¹ (C₃N₈ moiety).

Similarly, other substituted 4-thiazolidinones were prepared (Table 1 ; sl. nos. 19-36).

2-Aryl-3-*p*-(2',4'-diethylamino-*s*-triazin)-6'-ylaminobenzoylamino-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones : Thiolactic acid (0.01 mol, 1.06 g) was added to 3 (0.01 mol, 4.04 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) and refluxed for 5 h. The product was isolated as above and crystallised from methanol, (72%), m.p. 73° (Found : C, 58.43 ; H, 5.53 ; N, 22.03. C₂₄H₂₈N₈O₂S calcd. for : C,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	N % : Found/Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	150	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₈ O	27.60 (27.72)
2.	<i>m</i> -Aminophenyl	163	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₈ O	29.93 (30.07)
3.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	151	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₈ O	29.68 (30.07)
4.	Cinnamyl	110	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₈ O	25.33 (26.04)
5.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	122	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₈ O	25.09 (25.51)
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	169	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₈ O	25.13 (25.57)
7.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	98	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₈ O	23.41 (23.73)
8.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	117	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₂	26.10 (26.66)
9.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	116	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₂	26.33 (26.66)
10.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	135	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂	25.00 (25.80)
11.	<i>m</i> -Methoxyphenyl	118	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂	24.93 (25.80)
12.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	97	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂	25.34 (25.80)
13.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	127	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₂	24.00 (24.13)
14.	2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl	129	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₃	23.68 (24.88)
15.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	135	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₃	27.62 (28.06)
16.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	95	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₃	27.33 (28.06)
17.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	103	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₈ O	28.00 (28.06)
18.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-phenyl	85	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₈ O	27.93 (28.18)
19.	Phenyl	86	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ S	23.02 (23.43)
20.	<i>m</i> -Aminophenyl	109	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ S	24.96 (25.55)
21.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	164	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ S	25.12 (25.55)
22.	Cinnamyl	130	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₂ S	22.00 (22.22)
23.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	132	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ ClN ₈ O ₂ S	20.96 (21.87)
24.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	152	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ ClN ₈ O ₂ S	21.22 (21.87)
25.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	224	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₈ O ₂ S	20.20 (20.51)
26.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	128	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₂ S	22.08 (22.67)
27.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	152	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₂ S	21.92 (22.67)
28.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	120	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ S	22.00 (22.05)
29.	<i>m</i> -Methoxyphenyl	110	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ S	21.86 (22.05)
30.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	126	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ S	21.93 (22.05)
31.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	118	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₂ S	20.32 (20.81)
32.	2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl	128	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₂ S	21.20 (21.37)
33.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	148	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₂ S	21.20 (21.37)
34.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	131	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₂ S	23.93 (24.09)
35.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	163	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₈ O ₂ S	23.93 (24.09)
36.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-phenyl	138	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₂ S	24.01 (24.18)

(Table 1 contd.)

37. Phenyl	73	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	22.03 (22.76)
38. <i>m</i> -Aminophenyl	138	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	23.96 (24.86)
39. <i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	163	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	24.12 (24.86)
40. Cinnamyl	98	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	21.32 (21.62)
41. <i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	132	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	20.86 (21.29)
42. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	148	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	21.01 (21.29)
43. 2,4-Dichlorophenyl	158	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	19.80 (20.00)
44. <i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	148	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	21.98 (22.04)
45. <i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	118	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	22.00 (22.04)
46. <i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	63	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	21.06 (21.45)
47. <i>m</i> -Methoxyphenyl	127	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	20.87 (21.45)
48. <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	103	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	20.93 (21.45)
49. 3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	218	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	20.01 (20.29)
50. 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-phenyl	139	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	20.12 (20.82)
51. <i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	121	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	23.00 (23.46)
52. <i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	108	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	22.76 (23.46)
53. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	128	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	22.83 (23.46)
54. <i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-phenyl	124	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	23.10 (23.55)

58.53 ; H, 5.69 ; N, 22.76%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 3 050 (CH asym. for thiazolidinone moiety), 1 700

(C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 700 (C-S-C), 820 cm⁻¹ (C₅N₂ moiety).

Similarly other 4-thiazolidinones were prepared (Table 1 ; sl. nos. 37 - 54).

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